

The RePro technique: a new, systematic technique for rethinking care processes

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Redesigning care processes is challenging and requires a well thought-out technique that supports healthcare practitioners in generating process improvement ideas. In this paper, we argue that adequate support is still not available and present a new, systematic technique for rethinking care processes: the RePro (Rethinking of Processes) technique. The backbone of this technique is a set of process improvement principles. These principles are based on solutions that have been applied previously and seem worthwhile to replicate in another situation or setting. By inviting practitioners to go through the list of principles in a systematic way, the RePro technique aims to support practitioners in generating a rich set of process improvement ideas.

Research methodology: The backbone of the RePro technique, i.e. the set of RePro principles, is formed by comparing and integrating two groups of principles: *BPR best practices*, which primarily support rethinking administrative processes, and *TRIZ innovation principles*, which in their original form provide support for innovating products. To enable a systematic comparison and integration of these two groups of principles, four panel experts and a moderator were involved in a Delphi procedure. The resulting set of RePro principles was complemented with an application procedure to support practitioners in applying the principles.

Results: The development of the RePro technique led to a set of 46 RePro principles. All these principles address one of the following aspects of a care process: *customers, external environment, tasks, task order and timing, human resources, facilities, equipment and material, information, information and communication technology* or *physical lay-out*. The application procedure, which guides practitioners in applying the set of principles, includes the nominal group technique and multi-level design approach as basic ingredients.

Conclusion: The developed RePro technique has the potential to advance support for rethinking care processes.

Keywords: Health Services Research, Delivery of Health Care, Business Process Redesign, Business Process Reengineering, Business Process Improvement, Workflow Engineering, Lean, Six Sigma, Total Quality Management, Service Engineering, Pathways.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, many healthcare organizations are redesigning care processes to achieve efficient and effective patient care.¹⁻⁵ Typically, care processes include several consultations, diagnostic tests and treatments, as well as supporting steps, such as scheduling. In order to support practitioners in generating improvement ideas for these processes, a well thought-out technique is needed.^{5,6} In the absence of such support,⁶⁻¹¹ healthcare practitioners must rely substantially on their own experience and intuition to generate process improvement ideas.^{7,12} This reliance increases the risk on biased choices and neglecting interesting process alternatives.^{7,12}

In this paper, we present a new, systematic technique for rethinking care processes: the RePro (Rethinking of Processes) technique. This technique relies on a set of process improvement principles. These principles are based on solutions that have been applied previously and seem worthwhile to reproduce in another situation or setting. Examples of these principles are “control relocation” (move controls to customers) and “task automation” (consider automating tasks). As part of the RePro technique, practitioners are recommended to go through a list of process improvement principles in a systematic way. As such, the RePro technique aims to support practitioners in generating a rich set of process improvement ideas.

BACKGROUND

A typical process improvement initiative consists of describing the as-is situation, conducting an analysis of the as-is to identify process weaknesses, and constructing the to-be process. Whereas a lot of time is typically spent on describing and analyzing the as-is situation in a systematic way, process improvement ideas (to-be) are often generated in one or a few workshops using traditional creativity techniques such as brainstorming.¹³ Unfortunately, these techniques lack any guidance with regard to the kind of process alternatives that need to be considered, and do not provide a solution for the personal inertia to search for process alternatives that are different from familiar directions.⁷ These limitations restrict the systematic exploration of the full range of redesign possibilities.

Alternatives for traditional creativity techniques

A systematic literature review revealed that several alternatives are available for traditional creativity techniques.^{14,15} In particular, three kinds of techniques are available that, in contrast to traditional creativity techniques, offer guidance regarding the kind of process alternatives that are worthwhile to consider: *repository-based*, *case-based* and *rule-based* techniques.

A *repository-based* technique assumes the existence of a repository that includes specifications of numerous existing processes.¹⁵⁻¹⁹ Practitioners have to determine the core activities of the process under study. Subsequently, practitioners are able to explore the process variants available in the repository in a systematic way. The variants in the repository are structured based on the notions of process specializations, coordination mechanisms and process exception handlers. After a systematic exploration of the variants in the repository, practitioners can select the most suitable process design.

A *case-based* technique makes use of a library of well-documented previous business process redesign projects, i.e. BPR cases.^{15,20} This technique enables an efficient identification of relevant earlier BPR cases based on a description of several characteristics of the ongoing BPR case. The identified BPR

cases offer process improvement proposals that can be worthwhile to consider for the process under study.

A *rule-based* technique makes use of generic process redesign rules or principles that have accumulated in literature or practice to develop process alternatives.¹⁵ The premise of this technique is that specific process problems can be translated to generic process problems, for which generic principles can offer generic process solutions. An example of a generic principle is the parallelism principle, which states that redesign participants should consider executing tasks in parallel. As the technique's final step, the generic process solutions have to be translated to specific process solutions.

When comparing the principles of the *rule-based* technique with concrete variants offered by the *repository-based* technique and concrete process improvement proposals provided by the *case-based* technique, it can be concluded that *rule-based* techniques offer more abstract redesign guidance. Although this might be considered a weakness, this higher level of abstraction is likely to enable practitioners to generate more diverse and more original process solutions. In addition, *rule-based* techniques do not require the availability and maintenance of a database with either process descriptions or descriptions of process improvement projects. Based on the reasoning above, *rule-based* techniques form the basis of the new RePro technique that is developed as part of this research endeavour.

Rule-based techniques

In literature, two rule-based techniques that rely on a comprehensive set of process redesign principles can be distinguished: techniques that rely on *BPR best practices*, and techniques that rely on *TRIZ innovation principles*.

BPR best practices

The techniques that rely on *BPR best practices* make use of 29 best practices that are derived from a literature review.²¹ The 29 best practices are categorized in a framework containing seven categories (see Figure 1):

- *Customers*: best practices focusing on improving contacts with customers;
- *Business process operation*: best practices considering how to implement the workflow;
- *Business process behavior*: best practices focusing on when the workflow is executed;
- *Organization*: best practices considering both the structure of the organization (mostly the allocation of resources) and the resources involved (types and number);
- *Information*: best practices addressing the information the business process uses, creates, may use or may create;
- *Technology*: best practices focusing on the technology the business process uses or may use;
- *External environment*: best practices focusing on improving the collaboration and communication with third parties.

Although the set of BPR best practices has been successfully applied in healthcare,²² a critical remark needs to be made with regard to its completeness. The set of best practices has been gathered with a bias towards application in the administrative domain. This bias raises concerns about the completeness of the set of best practices for care processes. For example, in contrast to many administrative processes where digital information objects are mainly processed, many care processes require the active involvement of patients throughout the process. Due to this difference, other process alternatives related to the involvement of patients might become of interest. Consequently, further research is needed to investigate potential enhancements for the existing set of best practices.

Figure 1. BPR framework.

TRIZ innovation principles

The set of *TRIZ innovation principles* is a source that potentially offers these enhancements. TRIZ is the Russian acronym for “Theory of Inventive Problem Solving”.²³ TRIZ was developed by Genrich Altshuller and his colleagues in the USSR in 1946. Based on an analysis of thousands of product patents, product innovation patterns were identified. These patterns were translated into a set of 40 TRIZ innovation principles that provide concrete guidance regarding product innovation options. At first sight, *product* innovation principles do not seem to be directly relevant for rethinking care *processes*. However, care processes share several characteristics with products:

- Care processes face numerous synchronization challenges due to the existence of autonomous medical disciplines and specialized departments that require interdisciplinary cooperation and coordination. Products face, to some extent, similar synchronization challenges due to highly interacting product components.
- Care processes often require the physical presence of patients. Similarly, many products process physical objects (e.g. luggage conveyor systems).
- Care processes as well as products typically have to fulfill strict safety regulations.

Due to these three similarities, we argue that the TRIZ innovation principles have potential to provide new and complementary insights into how care processes can be improved. As far as our knowledge is concerned, the set of TRIZ innovation principles has not been used to improve care processes so far. However, several attempts can be found in literature that use the set of 40 TRIZ innovation principles to improve services or processes in other domains.^{23,24} Although promising, a more in-depth investigation of its potential is necessary. In particular, a systematic investigation should reveal whether TRIZ innovation principles (after adaptation to process improvement terminology) provide relevant enhancements for the set of BPR best practices.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this paper, we outline the development of a new, systematic technique for rethinking care processes: the RePro (Rethinking of Processes) technique. This technique relies on a comprehensive set of RePro principles that is formed by comparing and integrating two groups of principles: BPR best practices and TRIZ innovation principles.

The procedure that was used to systematically compare and integrate the sets of BPR best practices and TRIZ innovation principles was inspired by the Delphi technique.²⁵ The Delphi technique is a structured discussion technique which relies on a panel of experts who do not need to be in close physical proximity. Typically, the technique contains two rounds of questionnaires and anonymous feedback reports in order to reach consensus about a certain topic. The panel experts are encouraged to revise their earlier answers based on feedback reports that include replies of other panel experts.

A Delphi technique with four panel experts was developed in order to compare and integrate the two groups of principles. This Delphi procedure contained one preparation step and four discussion steps. The preparation step aimed at obtaining a full understanding of the 29 BPR best practices and 40 TRIZ innovation principles. Regarding the four discussion steps that followed, it was decided to take the set of 29 BPR best practices and related categories as a basis. Because care processes typically contain a large administrative component, it is assumed that all BPR best practices and categories are relevant in the context of care processes. During the four discussion steps, it was determined for each TRIZ innovation principle whether (1) it was already captured by one of the existing BPR best practices, (2) it offered a new relevant principle that could be added to the set of BPR best practices or (3) it did not offer a principle that was translatable to a *process* improvement principle. Based on this analysis, new principles and related categories were added to the BPR best practices framework in a systematic way. Each of the four discussion steps contained two individual rounds followed by feedback reports, and one face-to-face consensus round chaired by the moderator. More details with regard to the procedure can be found in Appendix B.

After the comparison and integration of the two groups of principles, a procedure was developed to support practitioners in applying the set of RePro principles.

RESULTS: COMPARISON TRIZ INNOVATION PRINCIPLES AND BPR BEST PRACTICES

In this section, we summarize the results regarding the comparison of TRIZ innovation principles and BPR best practices. All intermediate results of the Delphi procedure can be provided on request.

The results of the Delphi procedure related to the comparison of TRIZ innovation principles and BPR best practices are summarized in Table 1.

Comparison result	Number of TRIZ innovation principles
Principle that is already captured by one of the original BPR best practices.	18 (45%)
Principle that is a valuable addition to the original set of BPR best practices.	8 (20%)
Principle that is not translatable to a process improvement principle.	14 (35%)

Table 1. Summary comparison TRIZ innovation principles and BPR best practices.

The application of the Delphi procedure revealed that 18 out of 40 TRIZ innovation principles (45%) are already (partially) captured by the BPR best practices. More specifically, we identified 14 “is like” association relationships, three “parent-child” generalization relationships and one “child-parent” generalization relationship. An example of the first kind of relationship is the relationship between the TRIZ innovation principle “extraction” (separate an interfering part or property from an object or system, or single out the only necessary part (or property) of an object or system) and the BPR best practice “exception” (design processes for typical orders and isolate exceptional orders from normal flow). An example of the second kind of relationship is the relationship between the (parent) TRIZ innovation principle “partial or excessive action” (if 100% of an object or system is hard to achieve using a given solution method, then, by using “slightly less” or “slightly more” of the same method, the problem may be considerably easier to solve) and the (child) BPR best practice “extra resources” (if capacity is not sufficient, consider increasing the number of resources).

As part of the Delphi procedure, we also concluded that 8 out of 40 TRIZ innovation principles (20%) are valuable additions to the set of BPR best practices. Examples of these TRIZ innovation principles are “prior action” (perform tasks, before they need to be executed, or add tasks to smooth the execution of remaining tasks in the process) and “feedback” (consider introducing feedback). The TRIZ innovation principle “prior action” states that the required change of an object should be performed before it is necessarily needed and prearrangements should be taken to ensure that objects or systems can come into action from the most convenient place and without losing time for their delivery.²³ An example of an application of this principle in healthcare is asking patients to already undress in a preparation room before entering the treatment room. In this way, a medical specialist can immediately start assessing the patient without waiting for the patient to undress. As a result, expensive idle time of the medical specialist is prevented. Similar to “prior action”, the TRIZ innovation principle “feedback” offers a valuable addition to the original set of BPR best practices. An example of an application of this principle is inviting patients to fill in a post-operative questionnaire in order to identify possibilities for improving the quality of the care process.

For 14 out of 40 TRIZ innovation principles (35%), we concluded that the principle is not translatable to a *process* improvement principle. Examples of these principles are “thermal expansion” (use thermal expansion (or contraction) of materials, or if thermal expansion is being used, use multiple materials with different coefficients of thermal expansion) and “composite materials” (change from uniform to composite (multiple) materials). These principles are relevant in the context of *product* innovation, but are not translatable to principles that are relevant in the context of improving *processes*.

RESULTS: REPRO TECHNIQUE

In this section, we explain the final deliverables of the development phase: (1) the RePro framework containing the categories that are used to classify all RePro principles (2) the new RePro principles, and (3) the procedure that supports practitioners in applying the RePro principles.

RePro framework

The identification of the eight TRIZ innovation principles that we considered valuable additions to the original set of BPR best practices led to the extension of the BPR framework with two categories: *facilities, equipment and material* and *physical lay-out* (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. RePro framework.

The first category that we added to the original BPR framework is the category *facilities, equipment and material*. This category includes principles that are related to the number and type of available facilities, equipment and material, as well as the allocation of these non-human resources to patients. In contrast to many administrative processes, care processes typically make use of expensive facilities, equipment and material. Smart usage of them influences process performance in a positive way (e.g. in terms of costs and throughput times). For example, the usage of self-dissolving stitches improves the efficiency of the process by eliminating the need for removing the stitch.

The second category, *physical lay-out*, includes principles that focus on the physical arrangement of the process. Typically, rearrangements of the physical lay-out make other kinds of process changes possible. For example, positioning preparation rooms closer to treatments rooms enables productivity gains by moving preparation activities from treatment to preparations rooms. The absence of the physical lay-out category in the original BPR framework can be explained by the fact that digital objects instead of physical objects / clients are typically transferred in the administrative domain. In contrast to physical transfers, digital transfers are not highly influenced by the physical arrangement of the process.

Besides these two additions, we decided to adjust the name of four original BPR framework categories. More precisely, the original BPR framework categories *operation view*, *behavioural view*, *organisation* and *technology* were replaced by the categories *tasks*, *task order and timing*, *human resources* and *information and communication technology* respectively. We consider these new terms to be better aligned with process redesign terminology (in the healthcare domain). As results of the two additions and four small adjustments, nine RePro categories are distinguished:

- *Customers*: principles focusing on improving contacts with customers;
- *Tasks*: principles considering the (kind of) tasks that are part of the process;
- *Task order and timing*: principles addressing the order in which tasks are executed and the more detailed timing of task execution;
- *Human resources*: principles considering the number and types of available human resources, and the way they are allocated to tasks;
- *Facilities, equipment and material*: principles focusing on the number and types of available facilities, equipment and material, and the way these non-human resources are allocated to tasks;
- *Information*: principles addressing the way information is used or created;

- *ICT*: principles considering how information and communication technology is used;
- *Physical lay-out*: principles focusing on the physical arrangement of the process;
- *External environment*: principles addressing collaboration and communication with third parties.

RePro principles

Besides the eight TRIZ innovation principles and the two new categories that we considered valuable additions to the original set of BPR best practices, we also considered additional enhancements. More specifically, after the identification of eight new TRIZ innovation principles and two new categories, it was decided whether there was added value in adding a TRIZ innovation principle that was in a “generalization” relationship with a BPR best practice to the set of principles. In case of an addition, a decision was made whether keeping the related child or parent BPR best practice in the existing set of principles was valuable or not. In addition, the panel experts were asked to review whether existing principles within a certain category could be copied (with a slightly adapted name and / or definition) to another (new) category. Categories are describing process elements which can be addressed during a redesign project and it might be the case that a certain principle is relevant in more than one category. For example, principles that are relevant in the context of human resources might also be relevant in the context of non-human resources.

In total, 17 new principles were added to the original set of BPR best practices. An overview of these principles is shown in Table 2. The first eight principles are the TRIZ innovation principles that were directly added based on the comparison of the two sets of principles. The other nine principles are the additional enhancements. Besides adding 17 new principles, we also changed the “extra resources” principle (if capacity is not sufficient, consider increasing the number of resources) into “resource adjustment (HR)” (consider changing the number of human resources) based on the identified “parent-child” generalization relationship.

Name principle	Definition	Category
8. Prior counteraction	Add tasks to prevent the occurrence of an undesirable situation or to reduce its impact.	Tasks
9. Prior action	Perform tasks before they need to be executed, or add tasks to smooth the execution of remaining tasks in the process.	Tasks
13. Periodic action	Consider making an action periodic or changing the periodicity of an already recurrent action.	Task order and timing
14. Process-status-dependent adjustments	Introduce possibilities for adjusting the process dependent on the status of the process.	Task order and timing
40. Feedback	Consider providing feedback.	Information
36. Sustainable use	Consider to make use of material with reusable, dissolving, or evaporating characteristics.	Facilities, equipment and material
44. Reconstruction	Consider reconstructing the physical lay-out.	Physical lay-out
45. Flexible lay-out	Make the physical arrangement flexible.	Physical lay-out
29. Substitution (HR)	Consider replacing expensive human resources with less expensive ones	Human Resources
30. Forward-looking assignment (NHR)	Assign non-human resources in such a way that maximal flexibility is preserved for the near future.	Facilities, equipment and material
31. Buffering (NHR)	Consider to buffer equipment and material.	Facilities, equipment and material
32. Resource adjustment (NHR)	Consider changing the number of non-human resources.	Facilities, equipment and material
33. Specialist-generalist (NHR)	Consider to replace non-human resources with more specialized or more generic-equipped ones.	Facilities, equipment and material
34. Substitution (NHR)	Consider replacing expensive non-human resources with less expensive ones.	Facilities, equipment and material
35. Copying	Consider to use inexpensive copies of non-human resources instead of expensive original ones.	Facilities, equipment and material
41. Information provision	Provide the customer with information about what is going to happen and related reasons.	Information
46. Lay-out shortcut	Consider creating a lay-out shortcut.	Physical lay-out

Table 2. Overview principles added to the original set of BPR best practices.

A complete overview of all 46 RePro principles can be found at the end of this paper in Appendix A.

RePro application procedure

The application of the set of RePro principles is supported by an application procedure, which describes how the principles can be applied. This procedure is based on the *nominal group technique*²⁵ and the *multi-level design approach*²⁶. Firstly, we explain the design choices for the nominal group technique and the multi-level design approach. Secondly, we discuss the developed application procedure in more detail.

Design choices

Nominal group technique

Typically, multiple persons are involved in rethinking care processes. The *nominal group technique* offers a procedure for groups of individuals that are faced with an idea generating task. This technique is characterized by silent individual idea generation followed by discussion and voting. Van de Ven and Delbecq²⁵ compared this group technique with the Delphi technique and the traditional interacting group. In their lab experiment, they showed that the nominal group technique and the Delphi technique are significantly more effective than conventional interacting groups in terms of the number of unique ideas generated. In addition, the perceived group satisfaction was significantly higher in the nominal group technique condition than in the two other conditions. Based on these results, Van de Ven and Delbecq²⁵ recommend the nominal group technique for reaching group consensus in situations where people are easily brought together physically.

Multi-level design

Besides the fact that the RePro application procedure should enable multiple persons to work together on the redesign task, it should also provide a feasible procedure for dealing with the large amount of principles. In previous studies, attempts were undertaken to develop an algorithmic approach to generate a prioritized list of BPR best practices that are worthwhile to consider.^{12,22,27-30} Some of the algorithmic approaches require input parameters to be entered by practitioners such as the type of performance improvement dimensions that are most important.^{12,22,27,30} Based on the specification of these input parameters and an a-priori determination of the typical impact of a principle on these dimensions, a prioritized list of principles is generated. Although feasible, assigning weights to different improvement dimensions and other input parameters for a business process redesign project is a highly subjective process. Moreover, it is also not straightforward to determine a-priori which principles typically influence a certain process improvement dimension. Other algorithmic approaches make use of process (weaknesses) measures (e.g. a high percentage of control tasks) in combination with condition statements to come up with a list of relevant principles.^{28,29} Unfortunately, it turns out to be difficult to identify relevant objective measures for all principles.

Besides the limitations of the algorithmic approaches outlined above, it is also debatable whether the main objective of these approaches targets a highly relevant issue: improving the efficiency of generating process improvement ideas. In many business process redesign projects weeks or months are spent on modelling and analyzing the as-is process, whereas a few hours are typically spent on generating process improvement ideas in a workshop setting. Given this inequality, it seems questionable whether improving the efficiency of generating ideas should be a key objective of a new procedure that supports this task. More important is that the procedure ensures that practitioners do not get overwhelmed by the extensive list of principles and an effective application is facilitated.

Based on the reasoning above, we decided to make use of the *multi-level design* approach. This approach is not an algorithmic approach that leads to a prioritized list of principles, but an approach assuming that service systems can be designed on different levels of abstraction.²⁶ This approach separates concerns and starts with redesigning the to-be at a relatively high level of abstraction, i.e. the to-be service concept. Subsequently, two lower levels of abstraction related to the to-be process are successively considered. Although such an approach does not necessarily improve the efficiency of generating process improvement ideas, it improves usability by separating concerns.

Outline RePro procedure

The design choices for *nominal group technique* and the *multi-level design* approach led to the RePro procedure as outlined in Figure 3 and 4.

Figure 3. RePro procedure.

As shown in Figure 3, the RePro procedure contains 5 steps:

- **Introduction and explanation:** The facilitator welcomes the participants and explains to them the objective and procedure of the meeting(s).
- **Individual idea generation:** Each participant in the redesign session is asked to individually generate and write down a list of process improvement ideas. During this activity, the RePro principles are explicitly considered while following the multi-level design approach as outlined in Figure 4. The participants are asked not to consult other participants or share ideas with each other. This step is discussed in more detail in the next paragraph.
- **Sharing ideas:** After each participant has generated a list of process improvement ideas based on a careful consideration of the RePro principles, the facilitator invites the participants to share their

process improvement ideas, and records each idea. This round-robin process continues until all ideas are presented. During this activity, there is still no debate about ideas and participants are invited to write down any new ideas that may arise from what others share.

- Discussing ideas: After all participants have received the opportunity to share their ideas and all ideas are recorded by the facilitator, participants are encouraged to seek verbal or further details about any ideas of other participants that are not clear to them. The facilitator needs to ensure that everybody is able to contribute to the discussion, judgment and criticism is prevented, and no ideas are eliminated. New process improvement ideas might be generated during this activity.
- Voting and ranking ideas: After a final list of ideas is recorded, the ideas are prioritized by the participant using a voting and ranking process. Several different voting and ranking processes associated with the nominal group technique can be found in Delbecq, Van de Ven and Gustafson.³¹

Figure 4. RePro procedure: step 2 "individual idea generation".

During the second step of the RePro procedure, "individual idea generation", participants are asked to explicitly consider the set of RePro principles while following the multi-level design approach as shown in Figure 4. The multi-level design approach implies that all RePro principles are assigned to three levels that can be considered successively:

- Service concept: Includes principles that are related to the service concept, i.e. the positioning of the process in relation to its customers and third parties. More specifically, principles at this level focus on improving contacts with customers or try to improve the collaboration and communication with third parties. All principles of the *customers* and *external environment* category are assigned to this level. "Control relocation" (*customers*) and "outsourcing" (*external environment*) are examples of these principles.
- Main process design: Includes principles that are related to the activities that have to be executed in order to fulfill the needs of the customers. The principles of the *tasks* category are assigned to this level, e.g. "task elimination" and "prior action".
- Detailed process design: Includes principles that are related to the details of task execution, i.e. the

“when, who, with what, where” aspects of task execution. Principles belonging to the *task order and timing, human resources, facilities, equipment and material, information, information and communication technology, and physical lay-out* category are considered at this level. The “parallelism” (*task order and timing*) and “case manager” (*human resources*) principles are illustrative examples.

Although participants are recommended to consider the three levels successively, iterations between the different levels are allowed. At each level, several RePro principles are available to support practitioners in generating process improvement ideas. For each principle, participants are asked to think about concrete applications, i.e. process improvement ideas related to that principle. After a careful consideration of all principles, the RePro procedure continues with sharing, discussing, and voting and ranking the ideas as discussed in the previous paragraph.

SUMMARY

Improving the performance of care processes is challenging and requires a well thought-out technique that supports healthcare practitioners in generating process improvement ideas. In this paper, we argue that adequate support is still not available and present a new, systematic technique for rethinking care processes: the RePro (Rethinking of Processes) technique. The backbone of this technique is a set of process improvement principles, which is based on a systematic comparison and integration of two groups of principles: *BPR best practices*, which primarily support rethinking administrative processes, and *TRIZ innovation principles*, which in their original form provide support for innovating products. Examples of these principles are “control relocation” (move controls to customers) and “prior action” (perform tasks, before they need to be executed, or add tasks to smooth the execution of remaining tasks in the process). The RePro technique contains an application procedure, which support practitioners in applying the set of RePro principles. This application procedure includes the nominal group technique and the multi-level design approach as basic ingredients.

We contend that the developed RePro technique has the potential to advance support for rethinking care processes.

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Appendix A: Detailed overview of RePro principles

In this appendix, we provide the complete set of RePro principles.

Level 1: Service concept

A. Customers

The principles in the *customers* category focus on improving contacts with customers.

1. Control relocation

'Move controls towards the customers (patients)'

By moving checks and other operations that are part of a process to the customer / patient, costs can be reduced and customer satisfaction might increase. A disadvantage of this solution is a higher probability of fraud.

Example: Ask the patient, instead of the nurse, to pick up the drugs by the hospital pharmacy.

2. Contact reduction

'Reduce the number of contacts with customers (patients) and third parties'

The exchange of information with a customer / patient or third party is always time-consuming. Also, each contact introduces the possibility of intruding an error. Reducing the number of contacts may therefore decrease throughput time and boost quality. Note that it is not always necessary to skip certain information exchanges, but that it is also possible to combine them with limited extra costs. A disadvantage of a smaller number of contacts might be the loss of essential information, which is a quality issue. Combining contacts may also result in the delivery or receipt of too much data.

Example: Combine the hospital visit "recording of the heart activity (ECG)" and the hospital visit "cycling test". In the new situation, one hospital visit takes place in which both diagnostic tests are performed successively during one session.

3. Integration

'Consider the integration with a process of the customer (patient) or a supplier'

This principle is based on the supply-chain concept. An improved collaboration between the transaction partners (by performing intermediate reviews) enables possibilities for reducing costs and throughput times. The drawback of integration is that mutual dependence grows, and flexibility may decrease as result.

Example: The treatment plan of an oncology patient is determined by the internist in a discussion session with the patient's general practitioner.

B. External environment

The principles in the *external environment* category address the collaboration and communication with third parties.

4. Trusted party

'Instead of determining information oneself, use results of a trusted party'

Some decisions or assessments that are made within processes are not specific for the process these are part of. Other parties may have determined the same information in another context. Obviously, by making use of the information of a trusted party costs and throughput times can be reduced. On the other hand, the quality of the process becomes dependent upon the quality of some other party's work. Some coordination effort with trusted parties is also likely to be required, which diminishes flexibility.

Example: Trust the 24-hours blood pressure monitoring data as provided by a general practitioner, instead of re-executing the monitoring as part of the hospital diagnosis trajectory.

5. Outsourcing

'Consider outsourcing a process as a whole or parts of it'

Another party may be more efficient in performing the same work. The obvious aim of outsourcing work is to reduce costs. A drawback may be that quality decreases. Outsourcing also requires more coordination efforts and will make the process more complex. Note that this principle differs from the "4. Trusted party" principle. When outsourcing, a task is executed at run time by another party. The "4. Trusted party" principle allows for the use of a result in the (recent) past.

Example: Outsource the assessment of imaging images to a specialized center in India.

Level 2: Main process design

C. Tasks

The principles in the *task* category focus on the tasks that are part of the process.

6. Order types

'Determine whether tasks are related to the same type of order (patient group) and, if necessary, distinguish new processes'

Ignoring that several parts of a process are not specific for certain type of orders / patient groups negatively affects the efficiency of the process. Applying this principle may result in faster processing times and less costs. Yet, it may also result in more coordination problems between the different processes and less possibilities for rearranging the process as a whole.

Example: Create separate perioperative processes (everything happening just before, during and just after surgery) for children and adults.

7. Task elimination

'Eliminate unnecessary tasks from the process'

Several tasks within a process do not provide value from a customer's / patient's point of view, such as control tasks and redundant tasks. The aim of this principle is to increase the speed of processing and reduce the costs of handling an order. An important drawback may be that the quality of the service deteriorates.

Example: Stop providing paper-based, drug-related forms when all patients use a digital interface.

8. Prior counteraction

'Add tasks to prevent the occurrence of an undesirable situation or to reduce its impact'

"Prevention is better than cure" is the premise of this principle. Certainly, costs are involved in adding tasks. This investment can be recouped by throughput time reduction, quality improvement, and/or cost reduction due to preventing an undesirable situation or reducing the impact of such an event.

Example: Perform a rigorous pre-operative screening before a patient receives open-heart surgery.

9. Prior action

'Perform tasks before they need to be executed, or add tasks to smooth the execution of remaining tasks in the process'

Performing tasks before they need to be executed or adding tasks to smooth the execution of remaining tasks in the process has similar advantages and disadvantages as the "8. Prior counteraction" principle. The difference between both principles is that the prior counteraction principle has a "prevention" focus, whereas the prior action principle has a "stimulation" focus.

Example: Ask the patient with knee-related complaints to undress in the preparation room, while the diagnosis of another patient is still ongoing.

10. Task differentiation

'Consider the division of a general task into two or more dedicated tasks' or 'consider the integration of two or more dedicated tasks into one general task'

When applying this principle in its first most popular form, it is possible to design tasks that are better aligned with the capabilities of resources and the characteristics of the orders / patients being processed. Distinguishing dedicated tasks may improve quality and facilitate a better utilization of resources with obvious cost and time advantages. On the other hand, too much differentiation can make processes become less flexible, less efficient, and cause monotonous work with repercussions for quality. Note that this principle is in some sense similar to the "6. Order types" principle. The main interpretation of the task differentiation concept can be seen as a translation of the order type best practice on a task level.

Example: Differentiate the provision of perioperative information for patients with and without diabetes.

11. Task composition

'Combine small tasks into composite tasks and divide large tasks into workable smaller tasks'

Combining tasks should result in the reduction of setup times, i.e. the time that is spent by a resource to become familiar with the specifics of an order / a patient. By executing a large task which used to consist of several smaller ones some positive effects may also be expected on the quality of the delivered work. On the other hand, making tasks too large may result in smaller run-time flexibility and lower quality as tasks become unworkable. Both effects are exactly countered by dividing tasks into smaller ones.

Example: The composition of Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) activities: positioning the patient and setting up the equipment are composed into one task executed by an assistant.

Level 3: Detailed process design

D. Task order and timing

The principles in the *tasks order and timing* category consider the order in which tasks are executed and the more detailed timing of task execution.

12. Order-based work

'Consider removing batch-processing and periodic activities from the process'

Some disturbances in handling a single order / patient are: (a) piling up in a batch and (b) periodic activities, i.e. activities that are only executed at specific times. Getting rid of these constraints may significantly speed up the handling of individual orders. On the other hand, efficiencies of scale can be reached by batch or periodic processing.

Example: Do not discuss all oncology patient once a week during a multi-disciplinary meeting, but discuss every patient in a multi-disciplinary meeting immediately after arrival of all test results of the patient.

13. Periodic action

'Consider making an action periodic or changing the periodicity of an already recurrent action'

Executing activities with a certain periodicity can lead to efficiency of scales. However, this principle typically leads to an increase in throughput times. Note the contrast of the objective of this principle and the objective of the "12. Order-based work" principle.

Example: Organize information sessions for oncology patients once a week instead of providing information during consultations with individual patients.

14. Process-status-dependent adjustments

'Introduce possibilities for adjusting the process dependent on the status of the process'

By introducing possibilities to skip process parts or adjust resource allocations under certain conditions, e.g. extreme long waiting times, throughput times can be reduced. Application of this principle might have negative consequences for the quality of the process.

Example: Skip checking insurance data of patients at the emergency department when waiting time is long and perform these insurance checks afterwards.

15. Resequencing

'Move tasks to more appropriate places'

In existing processes, actual task orderings do not reveal the necessary dependencies between tasks. Sometimes it is better to postpone a task if it is not required for immediately following tasks, so that perhaps its execution may prove to become superfluous. This saves costs. Also, a task may be moved into the proximity of a similar task, in this way diminishing set-up times.

Example: Take blood from a patient before the consultation with the medical specialist instead of after the consultation, in order to enable a discussion of the lab results during the consultation.

16. Knock-out

'Order knock-outs in an increasing order of effort and in a decreasing order of termination probability'

A typical part of a process is checking whether additional (treatment) activities are needed. Any check may lead to termination of further treatment: the knock-out. If there is freedom in choosing the order in which different checks are performed, the check that has the most favorable ratio of expected termination (knock-out) probability versus the expected effort should be pursued. By first executing the checks that do not require a lot of effort but have a high termination probability, the least costly process execution is achieved. There is no obvious drawback of this principle, although it may not always be possible to freely order these kinds of checks. Also, implementing this principle may result in a (part of a) process that takes a longer throughput time than a full parallel execution of checks. Note that the knock-out principle is a specific form of the “15. Resequencing” principle.

Example: Perform the lab-test before executing the time-consuming CT-scan (assumption: termination probability of further diagnostics/treatment is equal for both tests).

17. Parallelism

‘Consider whether tasks may be executed in parallel’

The obvious effect of putting (sequential) tasks in parallel is that the throughput time may be considerably reduced. A drawback of introducing more parallelism in a process that incorporates possibilities of knock-outs is that the costs of process execution may increase. Also, the management of processes with concurrent behavior can become more complex, which may introduce errors or restrict run-time adaptations.

Example: Do not wait with cleaning the surgery room till the patient has left the surgery room, but execute these activities in parallel.

18. Exception

‘Design processes for typical orders (patients) and isolate exceptional orders (patients) from normal flow’

Exceptions may seriously disturb normal operations. An exception will require workers to get acquainted with the specifics of the exception, although they may not be able to handle it. Set-up times are then wasted. Isolating exceptions will make the handling of normal orders / patients more efficient. Isolating exceptions may possibly increase the overall performance as specific expertise can be build up by workers working on the exceptions. The price paid is that the process will become more complex, possibly decreasing its flexibility. Also, if no special knowledge is developed to handle the exceptions (which is costly) no major improvements are likely to occur.

Example: Refer surgery patients with a Body Mass Index (BMI) > 40 to a specialized nurse.

E. Human resources

The principles in the *human resources* category are mainly concerned with the number and types of available human resources and the way they are allocated to tasks.

19. Order assignment

‘Let workers perform as many steps as possible for single orders (patients)’

By using order / patient assignment in the most extreme form, for each task execution the resource is selected from the ones capable of performing it who has worked on the order / for the patient before — if any. The obvious advantage of this principle is that this person will get acquainted with the case and will need less set-up time. An additional benefit may be that the quality of service is increased. On the negative

side, the flexibility of resource allocation is seriously reduced. An order / a patient may experience substantial queue time when the person to whom the order / patient is assigned is not available.

Example: The nurse who is responsible for the execution of the intake of the patient is also responsible for executing all checks and discharging the patient.

20. Customer teams

'Consider assigning teams out of different departmental workers that will take care of the complete handling of specific sorts of orders (patients)'

This principle is a variation on the "19. Order assignment" principle. Depending on its exact desired form, the customer team principle may be implemented by the order assignment principle. Also, a customer team may involve more workers with the same qualifications, in this way relaxing the strict requirements of the order assignment principle. Advantages and disadvantages are similar to those of the order assignment principle. In addition, working as a team may improve the attractiveness of the work.

Example: Assign to each oncology patient, one surgeon, one internist, and two nurses who will take care of the complete handling of the activities of the patient.

21. Case manager

'Appoint one person as responsible for the handling of an order (a patient), the case manager'

The case manager is responsible for a specific order or patient, but he or she is not necessarily the (only) resource who will work on it. Contrary to the "19. Order assignment" principle the emphasis is on the management of the process and not on its execution. The most important aim of the principle is to improve upon the external quality of a process. The process will become more transparent from the viewpoint of a customer as the case manager provides a single point of contact. This positively affects customer satisfaction. It may also have a positive effect on the internal quality of the process, as someone is accountable for correcting mistakes. Obviously, the assignment of a case manager has financial consequences as capacity must be devoted to this job.

Example: Assign to each oncology patient a nurse practitioner who is responsible for all activities that are performed for the patient.

22. Forward-looking assignment (HR)

'Assign human resources in such a way that maximal flexibility is preserved for the near future'

For example, if a task can be executed by either of two available resources, assign it to the most specialized resource. In this way, the possibilities to have the free, more generalist resource execute another task are maximal. The advantage of this principle is that the overall queue time is reduced: it is less probable that the order / patient has to wait for the availability of a specific resource. Another advantage is that the workers with the highest specialization can be expected to take on most of the work, which may result in higher quality. The disadvantages of this principle can be diverse. For example, work load may become unbalanced resulting in less job satisfaction. Also, possibilities for specialists to evolve into generalists are reduced.

Example: Assign patients with knee-related problems to medical specialists who has specific expertise in this area, before you assign these patients to medical specialist with a more general orthopedic background.

23. Geographic centralization

'Arrange (technological) support to enable effective collaboration between geographically dispersed human resources'

By making use of information and communication technology that takes care of assigning work to resources, it becomes less relevant where these resources are located geographically. In this sense, this principle is a special form of the "43. Integral technology" principle. The specific advantage of this principle is that resources can be committed more flexibly, which gives a better utilization and possibly a better throughput time. The disadvantages are similar to those of the integral technology principle.

Example: Introduce a Workflow Management System to allocate the assessment of imaging images to experts who are working at two different locations.

24. Split responsibilities

'Avoid assignment of task responsibilities to people from different functional units'

The idea behind this principle is that tasks for which different departments share responsibility are more likely to be a source of neglect and conflict. Reducing the overlap in responsibilities should lead to a better quality of task execution. Also, a higher responsiveness to available work may be developed so that customers / patients are served quicker. On the other hand, reducing the effective number of resources who are available for a work item may have a negative effect on its throughput time, as more queuing may occur.

Example: The anesthesiologist is fully responsible for the pre-operative assessment and the surgeon is fully responsible for writing the discharge letter.

25. Numerical involvement

'Minimize the number of departments, groups and persons involved in the process'

Applying this principle should lead to less coordination problems. Less time spent on coordination makes more time available for the processing of orders / patients. Reducing the number of departments may lead to less split responsibilities, with similar pros and cons as the split responsibilities principle. In addition, smaller numbers of specialized units may prohibit the build of expertise and routine.

Example: All diagnostic activities regarding rectum cancer are assigned to internists (and no longer to surgeons).

26. Resource adjustment (HR)

'Consider changing the number of human resources'

The obvious effect of extra resources is that there is more capacity for handling orders / patients, in this way reducing queue time. It may also help to implement a more flexible assignment policy. Of course, hiring or buying extra resources is costly. These effects are exactly countered by reducing the number of human resources.

Example: Hire an additional nurse.

27. Specialist-generalist (HR)

'Consider to make human resources more specialized or more generalist'

Resources may be turned from specialists into generalists or the other way round. A specialist resource can be trained for other qualifications; a generalist may be assigned to the same type of work for a longer

period of time, so that her / his other qualifications become obsolete. When the redesign of a new process is considered, application of this principle comes down to considering the specialist–generalist ratio of new hires. A specialist builds up routine more quickly and may have a more profound knowledge than a generalist. As a result he or she works quicker and delivers higher quality. On the other hand, the availability of generalists adds more flexibility to the process and can lead to a better utilization of resources and a reduction of throughput times.

Example: Train all nurses in such a way that they are able to do the intake of the patients as well as monitoring the hearth activity of the patient (ECG).

28. Empower

'Give workers most of the decision-making authority and reduce middle management'

In traditional processes, substantial time may be spent on authorizing work that has been done by others. When workers are empowered to take decisions independently, it may result in smoother operations with lower throughput times. The reduction of middle management from the process also reduces the labor costs spent on the processing of orders / patients. A drawback may be that the quality of the decisions is lower and that obvious errors are no longer found. If bad decisions or errors result in rework, the costs of handling may actually increase compared to the original situation.

Example: The assistant of the general practitioner is authorized to fully take care of patients with straightforward complaints.

29. Substitution (HR)

'Consider replacing expensive human resources with less expensive ones when human resources are overqualified for tasks to be executed and consider replacing poorly-performing human resources with more expensive and more qualified ones in order to improve process performance'

The premise of the first version of the substitution principle is that human resources are often over-qualified for the tasks to be executed. Consequently, labor cost savings are possible by hiring less expensive (and less qualified) employees for several tasks to be executed. A drawback of this principle is that the quality of task execution might decrease. Also, substitution might have a negative impact on the speed of task execution. Vice versa, replacing inexpensive and poorly-performing human resources with more expensive and more qualified ones can be a means to improve quality and reduce process- and throughput times.

Example: Replace an orthopedic surgeon by a nurse practitioner who is responsible for the intake and after-care of orthopedic patients.

F. Facilities, equipment, and material

The principles in the *facilities, equipment, and material* category are mainly concerned with the number and types of available facilities, equipment, and material and the way these non-human resources are allocated to tasks.

30. Forward-looking assignment (NHR)

'Assign non-human resources in such a way that maximal flexibility is preserved for the near future'

For example, if a task can be executed by either of two available non-human resources, assign it to the most specialized resource. In this way, the possibilities to have the free, more generic-equipped non-human resource available for another task are maximal. The advantage of this principle is that the overall queue time is reduced: it is less probable that the order / the patient has to wait for the availability of a specific

non-human resource. Another advantage is that the most specialized non-human resources are most often in use, which may result in higher quality. Note that this principle is the “non-human resource” variant of the “22. Forward-looking assignment (HR)” principle.

Example: Assign orthopedic patients to the dedicated orthopedic surgery rooms, before assigning them to the multi-purpose surgery rooms.

31. Buffering (NHR)

‘Consider to buffer equipment and material’

Obtaining equipment and materials from other parties is often a time-consuming part in a process. By buffering / creating an inventory of these non-human resources throughput times can be reduced. However, costs are involved in keeping an inventory.

Example: Keep a sufficient inventory of sterile materials in an internal warehouse in close proximity of the surgery rooms.

32. Resource adjustment (NHR)

‘Consider changing the number of non-human resources’

The obvious effect of extra non-human resources or increasing the production time of these resources is that there is more capacity for handling orders / patients, in this way reducing queue time. It may also help to implement a more flexible assignment policy. Of course, hiring or buying extra resources and increasing production times is costly. These effects are exactly countered by reducing the number of non-human resources. This principle can be seen as the “non-human resource” variant of the “26. Resource adjustment (HR)” principle.

Example: Purchase an extra MRI scanner.

33. Specialist-generalist (NHR)

‘Consider to replace non-human resources with more specialized or more generic-equipped ones’

Specialized non-human resources can be used for a more limited set of tasks than generic-equipped non-human resources. Specialized non-human resources are typically able to improve the speed of task execution and deliver higher quality. On the other hand, the availability of generic-equipped non-human resources adds more flexibility to the process and can lead to a better utilization of resources and a reduction of throughput times. This principle is the “non-human resource” variant of the “27. Specialist / generalist (HR)” principle.

Example: Equip a number of surgery rooms in such a way that these rooms can be used to treat different patient groups.

34. Substitution (NHR)

‘Consider replacing expensive non-human resources with less expensive ones when non-human resources are over-equipped for the tasks to be executed and consider replacing under-equipped non-human resources with more expensive and more equipped ones in order to improve process performance’

The premise of the first variant of this substitution principle is that facilities, equipment, and material are often over-equipped for the tasks to be executed. As a consequence, cost savings are possible by purchasing less expensive (and less-equipped) non-human for several tasks to be executed. This kind of substitution might have a negative impact on the quality and speed of task execution. Vice versa, replacing inexpensive and under-equipped non-human resources with more expensive and more equipped ones can

be a means to improve quality and reduce process- and throughput times. This principle is the “non-human resource” variant of the “29. Substitution (HR)” principle.

Example: Replace (due to a decrease in patient demand) an expensive MRI scanner at the end of its lifetime with a less expensive one that is able to deal with less patients per hour.

35. Copying

‘Consider to use inexpensive copies of non-human resources instead of expensive original ones’

Instead of purchasing an expensive non-human resource, it is sometimes possible to purchase or develop a simple, inexpensive copy of it without negative consequences for the quality of the service delivery.

Example: Copy the electronic patient record as introduced in another hospital instead of developing a new electronic patient record from scratch.

36. Sustainable use

‘Consider to make use of material with reusable, dissolving, or evaporating characteristics’

Reusing materials and making use of material that has dissolving or evaporating characteristics is not only an environment-friendly solution, but also enables cost and throughput time reduction. However, the purchase of sustainable non-human resources is often costly.

Example: Make use of self-dissolving stitches for meniscus repair.

G. Information

The principles in the *information* category focus on the way information is used and/or created.

37. Control addition

‘Check the completeness and correctness of incoming materials and check the output before it is send to customers’

This principle promotes the addition of controls to a process. It may lead to a higher quality of process execution and, as a result, to less required rework. Obviously, an additional control will require time and will absorb resources. Note the contrast of the intent of this principle with that of the “7. Task elimination” principle and the similarities between the control addition principle and the “8. Prior counteraction” principle. Whereas the control addition principle focuses on checking information that is available, the prior counter action principle focuses on adding task that typically provide *new* information in order to prevent the occurrence of an undesirable situation or to reduce its impact.

Example: The nurse checks the discharge letter before it is send to the general practitioner.

38. Interfacing

‘Consider a standardized interface for information transfers’

The idea behind this principle is that a standardized interface will diminish the probability of mistakes, incomplete applications, and unintelligible communications. Consequently, a standardized interface may result in less errors, faster processing, and less rework. A standardized interface can be considered for internal information transfers between employees as well as external information transfers with customers and third parties.

Example: Invite patients to provide drug related information through a standardized interface.

39. Prior storage

'Instead of requesting information from an external source, store this information in advance by subscribing to updates'

Obtaining information from other parties is a major time-consuming part in many processes. By having information directly available when it is required, throughput times may be substantially reduced. However, costs may be involved in subscribing for periodic updates and storage of information. Note that this principle is a weak form of the "3. Integration" principle and can be seen as a specific variant of the "9. Prior action" principle and the information variant of the "31. Buffering (NHR)" principle.

Example: Store the information regarding all blood results in the patient's personal health record in such a way that these results are directly available during subsequent consultations with any healthcare provider.

40. Feedback

'Consider introducing feedback'

Providing feedback to employees (real-time or afterwards) with regard to process performance, supports employees in executing activities more efficiently and effectively. If feedback is already provided, changing the frequency of providing feedback can be considered. By providing feedback more frequently, performance problems can be tackled faster.

Example: Invite patients to fill-in a patient satisfaction questionnaire after the oncology treatment.

41. Information provision

'Provide the customer with information about what is going to happen and related reasons'

Customers appreciate receiving information prior or real-time in a digital or paper form about activities that are going to happen. Particularly, it is recommended to inform patients about diagnostic and treatment activities that are going to happen and the reason for executing these. This principle aims to improve the quality of the process as perceived by customers.

Example: Provide patients with a video on a website that introduces them to the endoscopic treatment experience.

H. Information and communication technology

The principles in the *information and communication technology* category focus on how information and communication technology is used.

42. Task automation

'Consider automating tasks'

A particular positive result of automating tasks may be that tasks can be executed faster, with less costs, and with a better result. An obvious disadvantage is that the development of a system that performs a task may be very costly. Generally speaking, a system performing a task is also less flexible in handling variations than a human resource. Instead of fully automating a task, automated support for the resource executing the task may also be considered.

Example: Introduce a barcode-system to automatically check the identity of the blood transfusion patient.

43. Integral technology

'Try to elevate physical constraints in a process by applying new information and communication technology'

In general, new information and communication technology can offer all kinds of positive effects, such as throughput time reduction (e.g. physical transport is no longer needed) and a better quality of service. The purchase, development, implementation, training, and maintenance efforts related to ICT are obviously costly. In addition, new ICT may arouse fear with workers or may result in other subjective effects; this may decrease the quality of the process.

Example: Introduce a digital performance board that shows the number and urgency category of waiting patients at the emergency department.

I. Physical lay-out

The principles in the *physical lay-out* category focus on the physical arrangement of the process.

44. Reconstruction

'Consider reconstructing the physical lay-out'

By reconstructing the physical lay-out of the process, walking distances can be reduced. In this way, it is possible to increase productivity and reduce throughput times. Certainly, costs will be involved in making changes to the physical lay-out.

Example: Do not make use of a central preparation- and after-care room, but create one preparation room and one after-care room in close proximity to each endoscopic treatment room.

45. Flexible spatial arrangement

'Make the spatial arrangement flexible'

Creating a flexible spatial arrangement is a specific variant of the "44. Reconstruction" principle. Using a spatial arrangement that can be easily adapted (e.g. by making use of movable parts), makes it possible to quickly react to changes in volume/case-mix of patients. The other advantages and disadvantages are similar to the reconstruction principle.

Example: Make use of flexible partitions at nursing wards in order to treat multiple patients in the same room (if necessary) without negative consequences for patient privacy.

46. Lay-out shortcut

'Consider creating a lay-out shortcut'

Introducing a lay-out shortcut is a specific variant of the "44. Reconstruction" principle. By introducing these shortcuts, walking distances can be reduced with productivity increases and throughput time reduction as a consequence. Certainly, costs are involved in creating these shortcuts.

Example: Create an extra door between two endoscopic treatment rooms in order to make switching between two rooms easier for employees.

Appendix B: Details research methodology Delphi procedure

1. Introduction

This appendix presents the final protocol that supported the execution of the Delphi procedure that was used to compare and integrate two groups of process improvement principles: *BPR best practices*, which primarily support rethinking administrative processes¹, and *TRIZ innovation* principles, which in their original form provide support for innovating products². In section 2 of this protocol, we briefly discuss the composition of the team that executed the Delphi procedure. In section 3, the Delphi procedure itself is described.

2. Team composition

The Delphi procedure team consisted of one *moderator* and four *panel experts*. The *moderator* was responsible for the development of the Delphi procedure. In addition, he was responsible for the coordination of all administrative activities during the execution of the procedure, and for chairing all discussion meetings with the expert panel. The *panel experts* were involved in executing the different steps of the Delphi procedure. All panel experts had followed several university-level courses with regard to Business Process Management, and had been involved in at least two business process redesign projects.

3. Procedure details

The Delphi procedure consisted of five steps:

1. Obtain a full understanding of the 29 BPR best practices¹ and 40 TRIZ innovation principles²
2. Consider the atomicity of the 29 BPR best practices
3. Identify relationships between the two groups of principles
4. Identify new principles and related new categories
5. Identify additional enhancements

Except the first step, each step contained two individual rounds and one consensus round. During the first individual round, each panel expert had to execute the step as explained in a detailed instruction document. After the first individual round, the moderator collected the results and provided an anonymous overview of the panel experts' results. During the second individual round, each panel expert was encouraged to revise her / his earlier answers in the light of the replies of other panel experts. After the second individual round, the moderator provided again an anonymous overview of the panel experts' results. This overview was input for the consensus round. During this round, a meeting was organized with all panel experts to reach consensus in a face-to-face meeting chaired by the moderator.

Each step of the Delphi procedure is explained in more detail below.

Step 1: Obtain a full understanding of the 29 BPR best practices and 40 TRIZ innovation principles

As a first step, the 29 BPR best practices and related categories, and the 40 TRIZ innovation principles were studied in detail by the panel experts. The 29 BPR best practices were gathered with the administrative domain as application domain in mind. Because care processes typically contain a large administrative component, it is assumed that all BPR best practices and related categories are relevant in the context of care processes.

The 40 TRIZ innovation principles are based on an analysis of thousands of product patents and support in developing new product designs. As discussed in our main paper, we argue that TRIZ innovation principles have potential to provide new and complementary insights into how care processes can be improved.

Based on the reasoning above, it was decided to compare the 40 TRIZ innovation principles with the 29 BPR best practices (as outlined below). In the remainder of this document, we often use the term “principles” to refer to “BPR best practices” as well as “TRIZ innovation principles”.

Step 2: Consider the atomicity of the 29 BPR best practices

Several BPR best practices include dichotomous scenarios (e.g. specialist-generalist: consider to make resources *more specialized* or *more generalist*). In order to facilitate an easy comparison between TRIZ innovation principles and BPR best practices, it was decided to identify the BPR best practices with dichotomous scenarios and to split these practices in two atomic principles (e.g. specialist: consider to make resources *more specialized*; generalist: consider to make resources *more generalist*). Table 1 was used by the panel experts to document their results.

BPR best practice (original)	BPR best practice (variant 1)	BPR best practice definition (variant 1)	BPR best practice (variant 2)	BPR best practice definition (variant 2)

Table 1. Documentation step 2.

Step 3: Identify relationships between the two groups of principles

After considering the atomicity of the BPR best practices, relationships between the TRIZ innovation principles and (atomic) BPR best practices were identified. More specifically, each TRIZ innovation principle was compared with the set of BPR best practices and the following relationships were considered successively:

- **Association** – An “is like” association relationship implies that the TRIZ innovation principle has a similar meaning as one of the BPR best practices.
- **Generalization** – A generalization relationship indicates that one principle (child) is considered to be a specialized form of another principle (parent). Both directions are possible in our case: either a TRIZ innovation principle can be a child of a BPR best practice, or a BPR best practice can be a child of a TRIZ innovation principle.
- **None of the above relationships**

The following rules were taken into when identifying relationships between principles:

- It is assumed that each TRIZ innovation principle has an “association” relationship with at maximum one BPR best practice.
- A “generalization” relationship is considered if no “association” relationship is identified.

- For each identified relationship, the panel expert needs to explain her / his choice.

The results of this step were documented by the panel experts in Table 2.

TRIZ innovation principle	BPR best practice	BPR best practice category	Relationship	Comments

Table 2. Documentation step 3.

Step 4: Identify new principles and related new categories

After the identification of the relationships, we investigated possibilities for adding new TRIZ related principles and related new categories to the set of BPR best practices. More specifically, we assessed each TRIZ innovation principle for which neither an “association” nor a “generalization” relationship was identified in the previous step. This assessment was aimed at identifying TRIZ innovation principles that can be translated into a new principle that is not covered by the existing set of BPR best practices. Here, translation refers to aligning the wording of the name and / or definition of the principle with common *process redesign* terminology. The following possibilities were considered successively:

- A TRIZ innovation principle can be translated into a new principle and can be added to an existing BPR best practice category.
- A TRIZ innovation principle can be translated into a new principle, but it cannot be added to an existing BPR best practice category. In this case, a new category has to be defined.
- A TRIZ innovation principle cannot be translated into a new principle (i.e. it is related to a characteristic that is specific for products, such a thermal expansion).

The following rules were taken into account while making the above decision:

- For each TRIZ innovation principle that can be translated into a new principle, the panel expert needs to explain her / his decision (in the form of illustrative application examples).
- For each TRIZ innovation principle that can be translated into a new principle, a decision has to be made whether the name and / or definition of the principle needs adjustment in order to align the terminology with common process redesign terminology.
- When creating new categories, one point of concern is whether several principles can be added to the same new category. Preferably, a category is defined such that it is broad enough to capture multiple principles, but specific enough to be meaningful.

The results of this step were documented by the panel experts in Table 3 and 4.

TRIZ innovation principle	TRIZ innovation principle (renamed)	TRIZ innovation principle definition (renamed)	Existing / new category	Comments

Table 3. Documentation step 4 (new principles).

New category	New category description

Table 4. Documentation step 4 (new categories).

Step 5: Identify additional enhancements

After the identification of new principles and new categories, it was decided whether there was added value in adding a TRIZ innovation principle that was in a “generalization” relationship with a BPR best practice to the set of principles. In case of an addition, a decision was made whether keeping the related child or parent BPR best practice in the existing set of principles was valuable or not. In addition, the panel experts were asked to review whether existing principles within a certain category could be copied (with a slightly adapted name and / or definition) to another (new) category. Categories are describing process aspects that can be addressed during a redesign project and it might be the case that a certain principle is relevant in more than one category.

In line with previous steps, the panel experts had to explain their decisions. Table 5 and 6 were used to document the results of this step.

TRIZ innovation principle	Relationship	BPR best practice	Category	Addition / substitution	TRIZ innovation principle (renamed)	TRIZ innovation principle definition (renamed)	Comments

Table 5. Documentation step 5 (added / substituted principles).

TRIZ innovation principle (original)	TRIZ innovation principle (renamed)	Relation-ship	BPR best practice	Current category	New category	Principle (renamed in new category)	Principle definition (renamed in new category)	Com-ments

Table 6. Documentation step 5 (principles copied to other categories).

4. References

1. Reijers HA, Limam Mansar S. Best practices in business process redesign: an overview and qualitative evaluation of successful redesign heuristics. *Omega* 2005;**33**:283–306.
2. Chai KH, Zhang J, Tan KC. A TRIZ-based method for new service design. *Journal of Service Research* 2005;**8**:48–66.